

Conditional Versus Non-Conditional Probabilities in Quantum Bound States and their Relationship to the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle and Statistical Mechanics

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Recently, there have been a number of papers in the literature dealing with the calculation of $S_p + S_x$ for quantum bound states. Here S_p is the momentum Shannon entropy $-\sum 2f_p f_p \ln(f_p)$ and S_x the position Shannon entropy $-\sum 2 W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)]$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. In addition, a number of papers discuss how the difference between $W(x) \text{Pop} W(x)$ and $[W(x) \text{Pop} W(x)]^2$ where Pop is the momentum operator indicates how quantum mechanics differs from classical physics. In this note, we try to consider instead the difference $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ and conditional probabilities $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$. In particular, we note that $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ are identical for the classical statistical mechanical oscillator and the ground state quantum oscillator, but $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$ are not. Furthermore, the difference between $W(x) \text{Pop} W(x)$ and $[W(x) \text{Pop} W(x)]^2$ may be more related to conditional probabilities than to classical versus quantum issues. In other words, one could have two classical systems with the same $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ and different $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$ as well. In addition, we argue that with nontrivial conditional probabilities, one should use $P(x$ and $p)$ when calculating Shannon's entropy. This leads to $S_p + S_x + \text{Integral } dx W x d/dx W$, where the last term, we argue, accounts for conditional probability. Interestingly, this last term is independent of W . We try to argue that it is proportional to $\langle [x, p] \rangle$. We also note that the Heisenberg uncertainty principle for x and p is sometimes based on properties of Fourier transforms. In such a case, it seems that the classical statistical mechanical result also has a Heisenberg uncertainty principle. For the case of the oscillator ground state it matches quantum mechanics exactly and one can calculate variances of p and x in the same way, it seems.

The Classical Statistical Mechanical Oscillator and the Quantum Ground State Oscillator

Consider a classical statistical mechanical oscillator in a dense gas with a potential $V(x)$.

1. At each point x , one has two particle elastic collisions: $p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$. Here p_i is a momentum vector and one has both conservation of momentum and kinetic energy. In addition: $P(p_1, x)P(p_2, x) = P(p_3, x)P(p_4, x)$ in order that probabilities do not change at each point x . i.e. the time reversed situation is as likely as the regular one. This leads to $P(p)$ proportional to $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$. In classical statistical mechanics, $P(p, x)$ is separable, i.e. $P(p, x) = P(p)P(x)$ and $P(x)$ suggests a spatial density.
2. Each particle is acted on by the potential $V(x)$, so if one has p_1 with kinetic energy $p_1^2/2m + V(x_1)$ at x_1 , one has $p_2^2/2m + V(x_2)$ at x_2 . Thus, spatial density must be

changing. In particular, $P(x)$ proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ accounts for this and the form follows from 1. It is not an independent condition.

Consider next the quantum oscillator ground state. Even though the wavefunction is related to conditional probabilities $P(x/p)$ and $P(p/x)$, one also has $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ which are not only completely analogous to the classical case, but identical. In particular, consider $W(x)=C \exp(-ax^2)$. Then, substituting into the time-independent Schrodinger equation for $m=1$ yields:

$$.5(2a-4a^2x^2) + V(x) = E \quad \text{thus} \quad a=E \quad \text{and} \quad V(x)=2a^2x^2=.5kx^2 \quad ((1))$$

$P(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-2ax^2)$ and $P(p)$ to $\exp(-x^2/(2a))$ because $W(x)$ and fp are Fourier transforms, so $W=\exp(-ax^2)$ and $fp=\exp(-x^2/a)$.

It is now necessary to compare ((1)) to the classical statistical mechanical format. Let us set $m=1$.

$P(p)$ proportional to $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ means $T=a = E$ and

$$P(x) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-kx^2/T) \text{ means } 2a = .5k/T = 2a^2/a \quad ((2))$$

Thus, in terms of $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, classical statistical mechanics and the ground state oscillator are identical. Furthermore, $P(x)$, i.e. the density, is a physical measurable.

It should be noted it is often argued in the literature that the difference between $W(x)$ $\text{PopPop } W(x)$ and $[W(x) \text{Pop } W(x)]^2$ is a measure of the difference between classical and quantum behaviour. Here, we seem to argue the difference is due to differences in conditional probabilities $P(x/p)$ and $P(p/x)$. It is possible to have a classical and quantum system with the same $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ (for the ground state oscillator), but different $P(x/p)$ and $P(p/x)$ values.

In quantum mechanics, it seems each momentum state carries an $\exp(ipx)$ (zitterbewegung perhaps) which contributes to the conditional probability and can be used to define averages which match classical values. For example,

$$P(p/x) = fp \exp(ipx)/W(x) \quad \text{so} \quad .5m v(x)v(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } fp p^2/2m fp \exp(ipx) /W(x) \quad ((3))$$

Note, here fp and not fp^2 is used. Similarly, one may calculate $P(x/p)$. Thus, microscopically, different conditional probability scenarios may lead to the same $P(x)$ and $P(p)$.

In particular, one has different values for $P(p)$ and x .

For quantum mechanics: $P(p \text{ and } x) = W(x) \int p \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$

while for classical statistical mechanics one has:

$$P(p \text{ and } x) = C_1 C_2 \exp(-p^2/2mT) \exp(-V(x)/T) \quad ((5))$$

To see how similar $P(x)$ or $P(p)$ results may be obtained, consider:

Sum over x $P(x)P(p/x) = \text{Sum over } x P(x)P(p) = P(p)$ for classical statistical mechanics, while

Sum over p $P(x)P(p/x) = \text{Sum over } x W(x) \int p \exp(ipx) / W(x) = \int p \exp(ipx) = P(p)$ for quantum mechanics.

A main idea is that one performs $P(x)$ averages so that in classical statistical mechanics one uses $\text{Sum over } x, p P(x) P(p/x) \text{ Function}(p) = \text{Sum over } x, p \text{ Function}(p) P(p)P(x) = \text{Sum over } p P(p) \text{ Function}(p)$

And $\text{Sum over } x P(x) \text{ Function}(x)$

For quantum mechanics, one uses:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Sum over } p \text{ and } x P(x) P(p/x) \text{ Function}(p) \\ & = \text{Sum over } p \text{ and } x W(x) \int p \exp(ipx) \text{ Function}(p) = \text{Sum over } p P(p) \text{ Function}(p) \end{aligned}$$

(An example would be $\text{Function}(p) = p^2/2m$ leading to a kinetic energy of: $\text{Sum over } p p^2/2m P(p)$)

And $\text{Sum over } x P(x) \text{ Function}(x)$.

Thus, for such averages, even with different $P(p/x)$ values, two systems (classical statistical and quantum mechanical) may yield identical results as in the in the ground state oscillator case.

Case of Entropy

In the literature, a number of papers, for example (1), deal with $S_p + S_x$, i.e. Shannon's momentum and space entropies. We have argued in previous notes, however, that one may use ((4)) as the probability in Shannon's entropy. This leads to:

$$\text{Entropy} = S_p + S_x + \int dx W(x) x \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \quad ((6))$$

Thus, there is an extra term which effects quantum entropy. This term is a consequence of each p plane wave carrying an $\exp(ipx)$ factor. It is interesting to note, however, that this term seems to be independent of wavefunction as:

$\int dx \frac{d}{dx} (W \times W) = 0 = \int W \frac{dW}{dx} + \int dx \frac{dW}{dx} W$ so:

$$\int dx W \times \frac{d}{dx} W = -\frac{1}{2} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, this extra entropy would not affect thermodynamic relations between high energy states or potential parameter variations. Nevertheless, it may be of significance because papers, such as (1), calculate $S_x + S_p$ in order to obtain a more accurate relationship than the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. These arguments are based on non-commuting operators such as P_{op} and X_{op} . Alternatively, some papers (2) use the relationship between Fourier transforms to obtain a relationship between the variance of p and the variance of x. For the case of the ground state oscillator, $P(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-2ax^2)$ and $P(p)$ to $\exp(-p^2/2a)$ so the product of the variances will be a constant independent of a, but one could apply this exact calculation to the classical statistical mechanical oscillator as it has an identical $P(x)$ and $P(p)$. Yet it seems that one does not discuss a Heisenberg uncertainty principle for statistical mechanics. According to the above arguments, it seems one could. For classical statistical mechanics, one has an average of p values at each point x and not a function $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)v(x)$ like in classical mechanics. Likewise in quantum mechanics, one has an unusual average of p at each point x. Thus, at a given x, there is a p spread in both quantum mechanics and classical statistical mechanics.

Consider next the idea of $[X_{op}, P_{op}] = i\hbar$. How does this appear in terms of conditional probabilities? We suggest:

$$\langle xp - px \rangle = \sum_{p \text{ and } x} [p P(p/x) x P(x) - x P(x/p) p P(p)]$$

$$= \sum_{p \text{ and } x} p \frac{p}{W} \exp(ipx) x W W - [x W \exp(-ipx) p \frac{p}{W}]$$

$$= \sum_{p \text{ and } x} -x W \frac{d}{dx} W - \left(\frac{d}{dx} W \right) x W = \int dx -2 x W \frac{d}{dx} W$$

This integral has already been shown to equal a constant 1 for any $W(x)$. It is interesting to note that the third term in the entropy of ((6)) is proportional to $\langle [x,p] \rangle$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue different statistical systems, in this case the classical statistical mechanical oscillator and the quantum ground oscillator, may have the same $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, but different $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$. On the surface, the two will look very similar if one only calculates

averages of functions of p or x alone i.e. $\int dp \text{function}(p) P(p)$ and $\int dx \text{function}(x)$. Thus, we argue that one has to be careful with recent statements in the literature which state that the difference between $W(x) \text{PopPop } W(x)$ and $[W(x) \text{Pop } W(x)]^2$ where Pop is the momentum operator, measure the difference between quantum and classical systems. We argue that the difference may be due to the effects of $P(p/x)$. As a result, for classical statistical mechanics (oscillator) $\sum \text{over } p \text{ } P(p/x) = 0$ because $P(p/x)$ is separable. Such is not the case in quantum mechanics and one has $\sum \text{over } p \text{ } P(p/x) = [d/dx W(x)] / W(x)$. In addition, given that statistical mechanics for the oscillator and quantum mechanics for the ground state oscillator yields the same $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, it seems that the Heisenberg uncertainty relationship for p and x should apply to the oscillator (and other potentials as well). At a given point x , one has a spread of p 's given by the probability weight $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$. For a given p , there is a spread in x as there is a density $\exp(-V(x)/T)$.

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